

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MANG'ENI****FIRST NAME: BENSON****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr GULMA**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is 2%

The author used the MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

Five key concepts in this response paper

1. Academic writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 6-12)
2. Punctuations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs British English (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 33-39)
5. Academic Writing Style, CMS CRIB Sheet, Latin Abbreviations, Expressions, and Sample Corrections to Papers (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 40-71)

ACADEMIC WRITING: ESSENTIAL GUIDELINES

1) INTRODUCTION

This is a Response Paper (RP) to my understanding of the period one-course pack, ACA-401/ACA-401D COURSEPACK (PERIOD 1) (Cleenewerck & Gulma, 2024). The course pack gives important guidelines for the essentials of academic writing. After reading this course pack, I understand seven broad vital aspects presented, which are academic essay writing, mastering punctuation, understanding and differentiating American and British English, plagiarism, writing styles, discussing the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) CRIB Sheet, and lastly, the pack in details discusses the Latin abbreviations and expressions used in the academic writing. Furthermore, the pack gives insight into the paper review process by the course instructors.

The coursework also included two videos. The first facilitated focus was on using style and formatting a response paper in Word. I appreciate that the presenter was very brief and precise to the point. The second video, provided by Dr. Kabiru Gulma, demonstrates how to track changes in MS Word. It is helpful as it keeps track of the changes and allows the paper's author to accept or reject them. Besides the provided resources, I spent many hours and days learning to use Zotero software for referencing, mainly on the internet and challenging YouTube, being my first time using it.

2)ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Chapter one (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7) explains the meaning and examples of academic essay writing. In particular, it defines academic essay writing as “*Nonfictional writing produced as part of academic work*”. (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, page 7) Moreover, it gives examples such as research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork published or not in journals, books, newspapers, periodicals manuscripts, theses, or dissertations, monographs; conference papers; book or literature reviews; explication; technical reports; translation; and students’ presentations (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). Importantly (Cleenewerck & Gulma 2024, page 7) give characteristic academic essays with formal prose, citations, and references, defined scope and objective, and contribute to new knowledge. “*By answering hypotheses and questions based on empirical evidence*”, as explained by (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). From the above explanation, essay writing is a special effort to write coherent and structured compositions to convey ideas, arguments, or narratives on a given field or topic, typically in academic or professional contexts such as evaluation reports, which relates well to my daily professional life.

After reading this chapter, I understand the three broad aspects of essay writing explained in the course pack: the basics of writing, the steps for writing a good essay, and the rule of thumb for writing a paper. The Course Pack outlines 12 steps for developing a good essay, but not linearly (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 7). The steps are. First, define and analyse the question and the key terms. Second, establish the points of view. Third, research the topic using credible academic sources. Fourth, take note of the preliminary study. Fifth, develop a plan and organise ideas. Sixth, draft the main parts of the essay (introduction, body and conclusion provided in a diagram on page 10). Seventh, reflect and review the draft. Eighth, seek input and review from professional colleagues. Ninth, complete or check the references. Finally, tenth, submit the essay as illustrated on page 8, figure 1—basic writing steps.

The course pack details eight rules of thumb for writing an outstanding academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 12-14), which must be understood before writing. These rules are as follows: First, state the paper’s central thesis before writing begins. Second, the writer should stay focused on theory and empirically narrow, not introduce unrelated themes. Third, the writer should always be factual and avoid general or sweeping conclusions. Fourth, the essay should be written clearly, with short sentences and paragraphs, and straightforward. Fifth, focus on readers delivering ideas; it should not be dull and clumsy. Sixth, never start a sentence with a subject and use passive speech, repetition, and long prepositional clauses. Seventh, the essay should be based on supported facts and have the proper citations. Views discussed in the essay should be seriously explained to avoid misinterpretation by being self-critic, reflecting and comparing with other scholars. Lastly, one should refrain from plagiarising by not using quotation marks and taking ideas without footnoting. I find this section very useful.

3) PUNCTUATIONS

The Oxford Learner's Dictionary defines punctuation as "*The marks used in writing that divide sentences and phrases; the system of using these marks*" (OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com 2024) further (Nair 2021) states that punctuation marks in English include the period, question mark, exclamation point, comma, colon, semicolon, dash, hyphen, brackets, braces, parentheses, apostrophe, quotation mark, and ellipsis.

The chapter had three objectives: one, passing knowledge of all the punctuation marks and their usage; two, explaining by example the use of punctuation marks; and lastly, differentiating between correct and incorrect punctuations, which are well-detailed and easy to comprehend. One of the Course Pack's most important aspects is a general rule: '*Use as little punctuation as necessary while retaining the meaning of the sentence*' (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 16). This makes writing more accessible to read and generally looks more professional. Therefore, a writer needs to know how to use each (Nair 2021).

4) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

This chapter discusses the two significant variations of the English Language: American English and UK English. American English is primarily spoken in the United States and some other countries in the Americas, such as Canada. Meanwhile, the UK or British English is mainly used in the United Kingdom, including England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland. Being a Kenyan, I use these two forms of English, which are mutually understandable without noticing the difference. However, Cleenewerck and Gulma (2024, 25-32) bring out enough differences between standard American English (SAE) and standard British English (SBE) in terms of vocabulary, spelling, meanings, syntax, style, connotations, frequency, punctuation marks use, expressions, euphemistic references, and sometimes even grammar and pronunciation to make them distinct from each other.

5) PLAGIARISM

Chapter four of the study pack focuses on plagiarism. It has three broad objectives: explaining plagiarism and how to avoid it, knowing when and how to cite and paraphrase, and inserting footnotes using MS Word. "*Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information.*" (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 34). In detail, the chapter from pages 34 to 39 explains, with examples, when to give credit to an author/s. Why should we mention our sources, explain the meaning of citing, how it is done, and when it is unnecessary? Lastly, the chapter explains signal phrases, a list of Works cited recordings, the format to follow, and how to achieve logical flow.

6) ACADEMIC WRITING STYLE, CMS CRIB SHEET, LATIN ABBREVIATIONS, EXPRESSIONS, AND SAMPLE CORRECTIONS TO PAPERS

Chapters five, six, seven and eight provide a more practical technical aspect of academic essay writing. Explaining the need and examples of style guides and what they constitute, CMS CRIB sheets, Latin abbreviations, and expressions, and finally, demonstrates a sample correction to papers. Significantly, it clarifies that EUCLID University recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) in chapter five. The study pack gives 15 examples of style aspects. *“A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent”* (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 41).

Chapter six explains the Chicago style in detail, giving its specifications and practical examples of how it is used.

“Chicago Style is the style of formatting books and research papers documented in the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS), 2003, and Kate Turabian’s Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, 1996 (both published by the University of Chicago Press). While sometimes reference is made to a “Turabian style,” this is simply the Chicago style applied to research papers. Revised Fall 2006.”(Cleenewerck and Gulma, 2024, 44).

Chapter six also provides an outline of the Crib Sheet’s contents. Finally, the Chicago style and usage, including abbreviations, capitalisation, compound words, italics and quotation marks, numbers, quotations, Chicago page formats, footnotes, headings and lists, tables, Chicago endnotes and footnotes, and Chicago bibliographies is explained with specific examples.

Chapter seven explains standard Latin abbreviations used in writing and provides two tables showing standard Latin abbreviations and expressions of technical communicators. Chapter eight illustrates a sample response paper with an example of the instructor’s response. Learn some of the dos and don’ts of writing a response paper.

7) THIRD PART: THE CONCLUSION

Learning from these study materials has enhanced my understanding of academic essay writing, the art of expressing ideas through structured prose, often for academic purposes. It has also enabled me to read more about the works of scholars like Michel de Montaigne and Francis Bacon, who emphasise the reflective aspects of academic essay writing. Further, I have also reviewed works of contemporary academics like David Bartholomae, who focuses on critical thinking and communication skills development (Eunson 2012, 224) in developing academic essays, which are not discussed in detail in the study material, though mentioned partially in chapter one under rules of thumb for writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2024, 12-24).

The structure of the study material is well arranged and easy to follow, which will be a good writing guide throughout my PhD programme. I want to understand it more, and I will apply the advice given. Additionally, using Zotero software for referencing is a new experience for me, which is still challenging, but I am determined to learn. Another important aspect is that EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian) style, while I have used the APA style in my undergraduate and post-graduate studies. Therefore, chapters five and six of the study material are beneficial in explaining the Chicago style and general guidelines.

REFERENCES

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